

**PARLIAMENT AND PUBLIC CONTROL AS DEVELOPMENT FACTORS OF
CIVIL SOCIETY**

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In the legal literature, various descriptions of the concept and essence of parliamentary control are given, which serve to develop the scientific basis of the process of parliamentary control. In our opinion, it is appropriate to clarify the concept of "control" before expressing the concept of parliamentary control. Control is a special activity carried out to study and check a certain event or the process of social relations. Various types of control are carried out in the system of legal regulation of social relations, that is, state control, parliamentary control, prosecutor control, ecological control, sanitary control, mining and industrial control, financial control, etc. These types of control differ from each other in terms of content. Therefore, it is necessary to clearly define the scope of the concept of control. In many foreign languages, especially in Russian, the terms "nadzor" and "control" are widely used in the theory and practice of law and are of great importance. The goals and tasks of these terms are common, but they differ from each other in terms of the object, subject, form, and methods of activity. The term "supervision" (supervision) is mainly applied to the form of prosecutor's supervision, while the term "control" (control) is a form of activity carried out by state authorities and administrative bodies. Therefore, the precise expression of the dictionary meaning of these terms in the Uzbek language helps to define the features of complex control activities of state bodies. The control (control) activity of the parliament differs in terms of its content from the types of control carried out in the state system.¹

It was emphasized that the rule of law, the separation of powers and the limitation of their powers, the expansion of the participation of civil institutions in the implementation of the important tasks of public administration and the socio-economic development of our country, that is, the important principles of building a democratic legal state and a strong civil society.

Special attention is paid to further expansion of the role and powers of the national parliament in the state policy implemented based on the principles of democracy in Uzbekistan.

A modern bicameral parliamentary system was established. The Legislative Chamber and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis are more and more effectively participating in solving important issues in the political and socio-economic life of the state and society. In addition to law-making, implementation of public control over the implementation of laws by state bodies and their officials is an important direction of the chambers' activity. The first President Islam Karimov's speech at the joint meeting of the Legislative Chamber and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan held on January 27, 2010, emphasized the need to strengthen such parliamentary and deputy control and improve its forms and methods. The implementation of legal documents, in particular, the effectiveness of the local executive authorities, increasing their responsibility, observing human rights and freedoms, and effectively setting up the work of the state mechanism are directly related to these issues. The implementation of parliamentary control will facilitate the in-depth analysis of law enforcement practices and laws to improve them.

A legislative base consisting of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and a set of laws was created by the conditions of rapid development of the country and international standards of parliamentary control. Controlling the implementation of laws, and decisions of the Oliy Majlis, controlling the spending of budget funds, observing human rights, forming state bodies, and appointing officials are among the main directions of the parliament of our country in fulfilling these important tasks. Radically increasing the role and importance of political parties, measures taken to strengthen inter-party competition and inter-factional struggle, and increase in the activity and professional level of deputies made it possible to raise parliamentary control to a new level. At the meetings of the chambers and their committees, it has become a good tradition to hear the reports of the members of the government, the heads of the executive structures on the implementation of state programs and other issues of their activities, the implementation of control and analysis activities by the parliament on the implementation of laws on the ground, and the discussion of its results, especially in mobile meetings. In this regard, forms such as parliamentary inquiries and hearings are widely used.

With the adoption of the Law "On Parliamentary Control", the procedures of parliamentary control, the specific powers of the entities that implement it, their tasks, and the mechanisms of cooperation with other state control bodies will be regulated, as well as a single base of regulatory legal documents will be created that will determine the consequences for those who violate the law. In Uzbekistan, not only parliamentary and public control tools have been created, but new, more effective types of them are being developed. This is a sign that your country is

firmly on the path to democracy.

Indeed, successfully solving the task of strengthening parliamentary control over the executive power depends to a large extent on the active participation of the mass media and the general public in this process. One of the most important tasks is to make the parliament a promoter of democratic reforms aimed at building a strong civil society in our country. In this regard, the participants of the roundtable noted that the adoption of the law **"On public control in the Republic of Uzbekistan"** developed at the initiative of the head of our country is of particular importance. This law creates a legal mechanism for the control of society and civil institutions over the activities of state authorities and management bodies. The draft law defines the types, forms and subjects of such control, the powers of civil institutions in their relations with state bodies, as well as the responsibility of officials for non-execution of legal acts in this field. In addition, it is envisaged to conduct a public examination of the drafts of socially important regulatory and legal documents. This allows the documents to be adopted to take into account the interests of different segments of the population.

It was noted that various forms of public control are used in practice in our country and they are strictly defined in some laws. For example, the community is conducting community control. Its tasks and powers in this regard have been strengthened as a result of the adoption of the new version of the law "On Citizen Self-Government Bodies". Many non-governmental non-profit organizations operating in our country are active in protecting the legal interests of the population.

The existence of such forms of control in Uzbekistan is a sign of the consistent development of democracy. In our opinion, the development of democracy includes several structural aspects. For example, this includes taking into account the interests of the population in the development of draft laws, the participation of civil society in this process, and the adoption of laws by the parliament and their full implementation in practice. These factors are used in practice in our country. It is also important to have the political will to implement these measures, i.e., they are being adopted at the initiative of the country's leadership. This, in turn, indicates that Uzbekistan is striving towards real democracy.

For the reliable growth of our development, we will adopt laws in the fields and in general and start implementing them. However, are our brave and noble people aware of such a legal situation? "The main issue is to convey the essence of the laws to our people and the responsible executives in time," said the President of the country Sh. Mirziyoev, to organize their execution properly and to ensure strict adherence to the requirements of the law.²

That is why it is appropriate for the Cabinet of Ministers to have a permanent representative in the Oliy Majlis to more effectively organize the cooperation between the government and the parliament in the sphere of control and analysis. Parliamentary and public scrutiny becomes essential to development. Isn't clapping a movement of two hands?!

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoev, to the Oliy Majlis dated January 24, 2020, "... it would be appropriate for non-governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society to draw the attention of state agencies to the problems of the population today and give their reasonable proposals.

For this, we need to establish a wide social partnership with non-governmental non-commercial organizations at the level of the country and regions and increase grants and social orders. Ministries and agencies should not sit on the sidelines and expand such social cooperation activities. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the activities of the public fund for supporting non-governmental non-profit organizations and other institutions of civil society under the Oliy Majlis.

It is necessary to clearly define the obligation to hold public consultations and public hearings when making decisions on extremely important issues related to the socio-economic life of our country and particular interest to the public. If the public says it's good, it's good, if it's bad, it's bad.

I propose to establish the Public Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan to further strengthen public control and establish close cooperation between the state and society.

It is necessary to establish practical cooperation between the parliament, government, and civil society institutions in the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations, and to organize regular parliamentary and public hearings on this issue.³

This proposal will help each of our compatriots to become a full-fledged participant in the reforms, and to feel a deeper sense of belonging to the present and future of the Motherland. Improving the public management system, introducing effective mechanisms of communication with the people, developing modern forms of public control, increasing the effectiveness of social partnership, developing civil society institutions, increasing their social and political activities, expanding the role and activities of neighborhood institutions in the management of society, as well as strengthening the role of mass media, protecting the professional activities of journalists are among these.

In recent times, as in all fields, fundamental reforms have been implemented in the development of civil society and the improvement of public control. Effective decisions were

made to actively involve the population in the management of public and state affairs, increase the legal culture and legal literacy of citizens, and ensure the openness of the activities of state authorities and management bodies.

The role of citizens, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and other institutions of civil society in the socio-economic and socio-political development of the country, management of society, and state affairs are increasing. To strengthen their interaction with the state authorities and management bodies, the Advisory Council on the Development of Civil Society was established under the President of Uzbekistan. Also, to form a comprehensive and independent system of comprehensive study, analysis, and evaluation of the reforms implemented in the construction of a fair and just civil society, to increase the efficiency of social partnership and public control mechanisms, to create a scientific and practical field for developing proposals for their further development, Civil Society development center was established.

In the activities of both structures, practical tasks such as creating an effective system of public control in each field and sector, and introducing modern mechanisms of effective cooperation with civil society institutions in the field of public control, based on advanced foreign experience in the country, are defined.

In these processes, it acts as a connecting bridge between representatives of the Public Chamber and state bodies. It serves as the main institution for solving socio-economic and socio-political issues in the country and improving social partnership relations.

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